

Blended Learning: The Need of Time

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Abstract: Blended learning is the mixture of traditional face-to-face learning and technology based distance learning. This approach is being used in most of the fields like industry, business. The field of education is not an exception for it. Blended learning has become a buzz word in this field and this approach has occupied the educational system in recent years. The years of pandemic of corona can be underlined for this. This research article throws light on the significance of blended learning. It talks about how blended learning helps the learners to learn. It also gives importance of blended learning in the views of teachers to plan a lesson, devise various activities for students to teach them with technology in distance mode and manage to impart quality education. The major objective of this article to find out how blended learning is useful for the students to learn and how it is useful for teacher to cater various learning facilities with technology in online and face-to-face mode. This article also provides information about the factors that affect the blended learning approach. Blended learning is very important and effective approach in the world of technology where the use of gadgets like laptop, mobile phone and tabs has become daily task of routine. This approach is flexible and easy to access as the aforementioned gadgets have made the layman a techno savvy. The most important feature of this approach is one can learn anywhere, anytime and with anybody. This feature makes the students stay motivated and learns at their own pace. This approach helps the students to reach the goal of their achievement in education.

Key words: Blended learning concept, students' perspective, teachers' perspective, advantages disadvantage, need of blended learning, conclusion

1. Introduction:

The term blended learning is emerging and growing rapidly in the world of technology. Blended learning is used in the corporate world to train the staff. It helps the staff to learn with distance mode. Now-a-days it has become one of the most popular trends to deliver knowledge. The academic world is not exception to this. During the pandemic situation of corona the world of education experienced blended learning that is online learning with the mobile phones, laptops and tabs. So many apps like zoom, Google meet, Google classroom were developed and practiced for giving knowledge or complete the academic syllabus. It is only these apps and online distance mode learning the process of imparting education did not cease and the student stay connected to their school and college for a long period of two years of corona. According to the US Department of education (Means, Toyama, Murphy, Bakia & Jones 2009) a blend of classroom and web-based teaching and learning offers access to the wider range of learning modes and methods for developing students skills and expertise as learners (Cleveland Innes, 2017) many finding on blended learning show an increase in learner's ability collaboratively, think creatively, study independently and tailor their own learning experiences to meet their individual needs (guide to Blended Learning chapter-1) the most important feature of this blended learning approach is one can learn anywhere, any time and with any one. This feature makes the students stay motivated and learn at their own pace. Self paced learning implies

solitary on-demand learning at pace that is managed of controlled by the learners (Harnvey Singh -2003) Blended learning has become a buzz word in the field of educational system in recent years. Many of the institutions are using this approach for conferences and various courses where the learners are availing of such conferences and courses online as distance mode. It saves time and money and helps the learners participate actively and express their opinions creatively. So in this world of technology and scenario of the gadgets like mobile phones, laptops, tabs which have made the layman a techno savvy. Blended learning is essential approach to learn and it is the need of time.

2. Objectives:

1. To study the concept of Blended Learning.
2. To study how blended learning is helpful for the teachers
3. To learn about the advantages and disadvantages of blended learning
4. To study the impact of Blended Learning on students and teachers.

3. What Is Blended Learning?

It is very important to see some of the accepted definitions of blended learning so that one can easily understand what blended learning is. Following are some of the definitions of blended learning.

- 1) Oxford Dictionary Definition of Blended Learning A style of education in which students learn via electronic and online media as well as traditional face-to-face teaching.
- 2) Graham (2006) defines Blended Learning as follows: Blended learning systems combine face-to-

face instruction with computer mediated instruction (P. 5)

3) Garrison and Kanuka (2004) define blended learning as The thoughtful integration of classroom face-to-face learning experiences with online learning experiences

4) Dr. Margaret Driscoll defines four different concepts in defining blended learning.

I) To combine or mix modes of web-based technology (e.g. live virtual classroom, self-paced instruction, collaborative learning, streaming video, audio and text) to accomplish an educational goal. (Driscoll, 2002)

II) To combine various pedagogical approaches (e.g. constructivism, behaviorism, cognitivism) to produce an optimal learning outcome with or without instructional technology (Driscoll, 2002)

III) To combine any form of instructional technology (e.g. videotape, CD-ROM, web-based training, film) with face-to-face instructor- led training. (Driscoll, 2002)

IV) To mix or combine instructional technology with actual job tasks in order to create a harmonious effect of learning and working.

4. Blended Learning In Students' Perspective:

Blended learning provides the students with ample opportunities to learn face-to-face and access the modern technologies at the same time. Students can develop various skills among themselves. Blended learning can be seen in students' perspective with help of the following points mentioned by Lalima, kiran Lata Dangwal in their article Blended Learning: An Innovative Approach.

I) Face-to –face teaching: Blended learning provides the students with ample opportunities to have interactions with their instructors and their peers. They can be influenced by the personality, behavior and value of the teacher. The students can give immediate feedback which is useful in teaching learning process.

II) Peer group interaction: Students can learn informally in the school campus. They can have good communication with their peer groups and learn together on the school ground.

III) Group discussion and exchange of ideas: In classroom teaching students can discuss with their friends in their groups. They can exchange their own ideas. This helps the students to develop their confidence, remove hesitation and develop the skill of communication.

IV) Virtual class room: In virtual class the students can learn as per the mantra anywhere, anytime and with anyone. The students can learn with anyone who admits them in their virtual classroom. They can learn with their friends, teachers and other unknown person who is a part of the virtual class. The virtual class can provide the students with the

guidance of various experts by which they can enhance their knowledge.

V) Use of You Tube for expert lectures: There are number of videos on You Tube available for the students to learn a particular topic. The institutions like Grade up. Uncademy have posted the videos of expert lecturers on a particular topic. These videos are available on You Tube after they have taken online class. It means the students can attend the online class as well as watch the videos after the class for consolidation. The institution where the students learns can also upload their videos on You Tube so that the student can watch the videos of his /her own teachers and feel at home.

VI) Webinars: Now-a-days there are so many webinars for the students who wish take part in. Webinar is a feature of blended learning that is ICT supported format webinars can be arranged on Zoom, Google Meet, Skype, Google Talk etc. The students can take part in such webinars and express their opinions even they can present their papers. (Lalima, kiran Lata Dangwal,2017)

5. Blended Learning In Teachers' Perspective:

I) well versed teachers: The teachers become expert in preparing their won materials like audio, videos, PPTs etc. They can develop their expertise in both traditional face-to-face training and online training. Blended learning makes the teachers to develop content in digital format. They become good at browsing internet and finding the right study material for their topic. They can handle various apps like Zoom, Google Meet, Skype, Google Talk etc. They can schedule their meetings and webinars and convey it on what's app groups.

II) Blended learning develop scientific attitude among the teachers: This is an important aspect that the teachers can develop scientific attitude while dealing with blended learning. They can be optimistic and develop problem solving skills. They use all the technology with positive attitude and the same attitude percolates from teacher to students.

III) Wider outlook: The teachers accepts the new changes and innovative ideas emerging on daily basis. They develop positive attitude and wider outlook and become flexible to accept the changes.

IV) Teachers become tolerant in blended learning: The students can voice their opinions in face-to-face learning and in online learning. The teachers listens to all the opinions of the students and the teacher gives his/her opinion. This is a good platform everybody to express opinions and listen to the other participants' opinion.

V) Monitors the group discussion: The teacher who is applying blended learning can manage the groups of the students and monitors the group discussion. He gives space for the students to express their opinions. He manages the group

discussion in face-to-face learning and online learning too. (Lalima, kiran Lata Dangwal,2017)

6. Advantages of Blended Learning:

- ❖ Blended learning offers more flexibility in the learning process.
- ❖ Blended learning allows for various learning activities, teaching approaches, pacing and students grouping.
- ❖ Students enjoy a combination of face-to-face and online learning.
- ❖ Blended learning provides students with opportunities to interact with faculty staff as well as the peers.
- ❖ Blended learning establishes bonding between teacher and students.
- ❖ Blended learning helps to learn individually.
- ❖ It allows students to work at their own pace.

7. Disadvantages Of Blended Learning:

- ❖ Blended learning needs technical resources or tools. These tools need to be reliable, easy to use and update.
- ❖ Good internet connection is important. Sometimes it gets disturbed.
- ❖ IT literacy can be one of the barriers.
- ❖ Sometimes the students can do malpractice while in meeting or learning online.

There are many advantages than the disadvantages. So it is important to focus more on advantages and not on the disadvantages because these advantages can be overcome.

8. Impact on Students and Teachers: Blended learning is an emerging approach which helps the students and teachers to make teaching and learning process easy as well as innovative. The teachers are now a days devising their lesson plans keeping the online material in mind. They use various pictures, graphs, photographs for their lessons. Now a days it has become very common to use videos relevant to the lesson in the classroom. The teachers teach offline and online at the same time. This is nothing but the use of blended learning. The students enjoy the teaching of the teacher in the class and they also use online material for their self study. Their presentations are becoming attractive and their performance the class is becoming praiseworthy due to only the online and offline learning. It is considerable that the blended learning is now spreading its roots in the students learning and the teachers teaching.

9. Need Have Blended Learning: In those old good days the education used to be given face-to-face in person. When the technology entered in the life of human being, the face-to-face education started taking place of online distance education. There are number of electronic gadgets help the students to take education online. The revolution in technology is not going to stop. Everyday new inventions are taking place. In such surroundings

teachers should cope with the speed of inventions and go with them. So it is needed to learn with the combination of both face-to-face and online learning.

10. Conclusion: Blended learning has now become vary much familiar with the students and the teachers as it is very useful and needful in the perspectives of both of them. The technology is now a part and parcel of human's life. Nothing is possible without the technology and various electronic gadgets which are in the reach of the human. If this gadgets and all the technology are used in the teaching learning process, it would be easy to impart knowledge and be receptive of knowledge. The coming generations would have more gadgets and much more advanced technology in their hands so blended learning is the need of time.

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